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Community-based Ecotourism as an Effective Tool for Sustainable Development of Indigenous Communities: A Study of Khasia Communities Living in Greater Sylhet

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Abstract:

Indigenous communities are the backward side among the inhabitants in most of the countries in the world. Usually they are the deprived and less developed part of the societies worldwide. The indigenous communities living in Bangladesh specially the Khasis are far away from all kinds of development and facilities. Ecotourism, with its potential to generate income and employment and its promise to protect natural environment for local communities, has been considered an important agent for indigenous community development since the growth in demand for cultural tourism began in the early 1990s. It has been argued that, as a result of ecotourism, indigenous populations' living standards and quality of life can be enhanced, and indigenous resources can be protected. In contrast, without community control, more often than not, ecotourism has contributed to unfair distribution of tourism benefits and deterioration of cultural and natural resources in indigenous communities. As a result, empowering indigenous communities to control ecotourism has been advocated as an integral component of sustainable tourism. In this sense, community-based ecotourism is often promoted as an effective mechanism for the empowerment of indigenous communities, allowing them to participate in decision making about, and control over, tourism development. This study evaluated the potential of the Community-based Ecotourism development for empowering the indigenous Khasia people who live in different districts of Sylhet Division as Sunamgonj, Moulobhibazar and Sylhet. Key informant interviews, secondary data and survey questionnaires were used as research tools to examine collaborative efforts of key stakeholders to empower the Khasia community to have control over, and assess the level of community participation in, the Khasia Community-based Ecotourism development. This analysis also includes the evaluation of the perceptions of the Khasis with regard to the impacts of the development on the economic, psychological, social and political lives of their people. The study results reveal that power re-

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distribution among the stakeholders involved in a collaborative process in Khasia Community-based Ecotourism planning and implementation had the potential to be a crucial component in facilitating empowerment of the Khasia community. The findings indicate that the Khasia Community-based Ecotourism initiative was perceived as an important tool for enhancing the psychological, social and political empowerment of the Khasia community, although the capacity of the project to contribute direct economic benefits to the community is limited. The thesis concludes that community-based ecotourism has the potential to contribute to a form of sustainable tourism for indigenous people of Khasia community living different areas of when there is an effective collaboration with indigenous people. This is most effectively achieved when indigenous people have the ability to have control over, and make decisions about, the development based on their own interests.

The research finds out that thousands of people in the different Khasia communities or Punjies are greatly dependant on its natural resources. However, the research observed that the forest and other natural resources are degrading and increases the sufferings of inhabitant people due to unsustainable utilization of its resources development. Ironically, ecotourism is the environment friendly and economically profitable form of tourism that safeguard for the ecosystem of hills and forests. Practically, where the Khasis lie and their surroundings have a tremendous scope for ecotourism and alternative livelihood. The Khasia inhabitants are keen to develop different kinds of handicraft, cultural activities and food processed items that have a significant value for the development of sustainable ecotourism. Finally, the research also focus on a ecologically based sustainable planning approach with recommendations on 'how the existing barriers conforing Khasia communities could be solved by using short and long term approach of sustainable ecotourism.'

Key words: *ecotourism, ecology, sustainable, community, development, conservation, empowerment.*